

A Continent at Risk: Interrogating the Power Dynamics in Hazardous Waste Trade in Africa

Goodman Arogo

Post Graduate Candidate in International Relations

Department of Political Science

Niger Delta University

Wilberforce Island

Bayelsa State

goodmanarogo@gmail.com

&

***Olawari D. J. Egbe, Ph.D.**

Department of Political Science

Niger Delta University

Wilberforce Island

Bayelsa State

odjegbe@gmail.com

*Corresponding author

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Abstract

This paper examines the complex dynamics and implications of hazardous waste trade within the context of international relations and resource governance in Africa. It explores the roles of the various players/actors into trade in hazardous waste such as state parties, and private parties such as transnational corporations (TNCs). It utilises qualitative approaches; especially the use of secondary sources as journal articles, textbooks, and online sources in its methodology. The paper discovers that there are disparities in the power dynamics between exporting and importing states into hazardous trade in waste, the prevalence of illegal dumping practices, and the challenges faced by African states in enforcing environmental regulations and holding transnational corporations accountable for their actions. In order to mitigate the negative effects

of hazardous waste trading and to promote sustainable development on the continent, the paper emphasises the urgent need to strengthen regulatory frameworks, increase transparency, and enhance cooperations among stakeholders. It contributes to the understanding of the complex web of political, economic, and environmental factors shaping the international politics of hazardous waste trade in Africa.

Keywords: Politics, Trade, Hazardous Waste, Africa

Introduction

In economic discourse, the Heckscher-Ohlin Model, dictates that differences in factor endowments amongst nations, compels trade among nations necessary, if not mandatory (Kopp, 2024). There is convergence amongst most economists who argue that international trade improves living standards worldwide. The accruable benefits from international trade are enormous and immeasurable to all countries of the world; several times, nations benefit more from trade with one another (McDonald, 2009). However, while the benefits from international trade are appreciated, incontestable and cannot be overemphasised; however, both within countries and between governments, trade can be one of the most divisive political topics (Reuveny & Kang, 1996; Madeira, 2014; Dorfman, 2016); especially that it can be harmful to sovereign states in diverse ways (FAO, 2022).

For example, international trade is capable of causing damage to human health, the economy of sovereign states, insecurity through illicit economies (such as smuggling through drug trafficking; human trafficking, prostitution; deforestation through illegal trade in timber, timber logging, trade in antiquities, etc.); illicit fishing, piracy, oil theft/bunkering, arms trafficking and the eventual proliferation of arms in the continent, etc. still international trade harms the environment through the transportation of hazardous or toxic wastes, trade in endangered species, exchange of pesticides, pollution of the marine and terrestrial environments (Frankel, 2009).

Particularly, international trade in hazardous waste presents peculiar complex and pressing issues, particularly in vulnerable African communities. While international agreements such as the 1989 Basel Convention aims to regulate the transboundary movement and disposal of hazardous waste, there are ongoing challenges and controversies surrounding the trade in hazardous waste in Africa that undermines the efficacy of regulatory instruments (Agbor, 2016). Research indicates that African states are disproportionately affected by the transboundary movement of hazardous waste, with detrimental effects on public health, environmental degradation, and socioeconomic development; however, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding of the intricate web of actors, interests, and power dynamics involved in the international politics of trade in hazardous waste in the African context (Atteh, 1993).

This study addresses this gap by examining the following key problems related to the international politics of trade in hazardous waste in selected African states. First, is the lack of effective regulation despite the existence of international agreements such as the Basel Convention (Agbor, 2016). There are expressed concerns over the effectiveness of regulations governing the trade in hazardous waste in African states. Studies have shown that regulatory

frameworks may be inadequate or poorly enforced, leading to loopholes and opportunities for illegal dumping and improper disposal of hazardous waste (Oteng-Ababio, 2018).

Second, is the power dynamics and environmental justice at play in the trade in hazardous waste which is often characterised by global power imbalance, with developed states exporting hazardous wastes to developing states. This raises questions of environmental justice and equity, as African states may bear a disproportionate burden of the environmental and health impacts of hazardous waste disposal (Doyle, 2017). Third, economic incentives and trade pressures that play significant roles in driving the trade in hazardous waste, with financial incentives influencing decisions to accept the importation of waste. African states facing dire economic hardship may be tempted to accept waste imports for monetary gains, potentially overlooking the environmental and social consequences of such actions (Sanchez, 1994).

Fourth, is the governance and capacity constraints, limited resources, and capacity constraints that weaken governance structures among African states that pose challenges to effective regulation and management of hazardous waste. The lack of institutional capacity, technical expertise, and financial resources often impede efforts to monitor and control trade in hazardous waste which leads to environmental and health risks for local communities (Doe, 2020); and fifth, the environmental and health impacts caused by the improper disposal and management of hazardous waste often have severe consequences, including soil and water contaminations, air pollution, and adverse health effects on communities living near toxic waste sites. Trade in hazardous waste raises concerns over the potential long-term environmental degradation and health risks faced by vulnerable African populations.

In light of the foregoing problems, this paper explores the dynamics of international politics of trade in hazardous waste in selected African states. The objective of this paper is to examine the complex dynamics and implications of hazardous waste trade in Africa within the context of international relations and resource governance. It does this by exploring the roles of the various players/actors into hazardous waste such as state parties, and private parties like transnational corporations (TNCs). The paper insists that by addressing the regulatory gaps, power dynamics, economic interests, governance challenges, and environmental impacts associated with the trade in hazardous waste, it aims to contribute to the development of more effective and sustainable solutions for managing hazardous waste in Africa.

To do the foregoing task, the rest of the paper is structured thus; following this introduction is Section II, the extant literature of the paper; dwelling on amongst other issues, including historicising hazardous trade in waste, understanding the international politics of trade in hazardous waste and stakeholder perspectives on trade in hazardous waste. Section III makes a critical assessment of the international politics of trade in hazardous waste. Section IV concludes the paper.

Extant Literature

There is a marked difference between legal and illegal trade in hazardous waste. Interestingly, not all trade in hazardous waste that is classified as illegal (Baggs, 2009). However, trade in hazardous waste becomes only illicit when it is:

undertaken without state permission, when contracts and concessions are secured through corruption or intimidation, when services involve fraud (e.g., false treatment of hazardous waste), and...Such illegal activities can have significant impacts on the health and sustainability of local populations and ecosystems. (FATF, 2021, p. 9)

This section examines literature related to the international politics of trade in hazardous waste in Africa under the following subthemes:

a. Historicising Hazardous Waste Trade: From the Local to International Scales

Hazardous waste refers to the global exchange of hazardous waste materials for recycling, disposal or treatment. This practice has been around for several decades and has had far-reaching environmental, social, and political implications (Strohm, 1993; Clapp, 1994). Hazardous waste trade on an international scale has a long and complex history with various significant developments shaping the current landscape of global waste management (Anyinam, 1991; Bisschop, 2016). Trade in hazardous waste can be traced back to the 1960s and 1970s when industrialised states of the global North began exporting hazardous waste to developing states in the global South with less stringent regulations. This practice was driven by economic considerations as it was often cheaper to export waste to states with less stringent domestic environmental regulations governing the management of hazardous waste. However, the trade in hazardous waste soon attracted criticism from environmentalists and human rights activists, who raised concern about the risks posed to local communities in receiving states.

These concerns were highlighted in the 1980s by high-profile cases like the Probo Koala incident in 2006, involving the dumping of toxic waste in the Cote d'Ivoire by a Dutch company, and which resulted in widespread health and environmental impacts (Puckett, 2003). This singular incident highlighted the need for stronger regulations and enforcement mechanisms to prevent the illegal trafficking of hazardous waste. The 1989 Basel Convention on the Control of Trans-boundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and Their Disposal, amongst others, was one of the key international action efforts at curtailing hazardous waste trade. The Basel Convention was a response to the growing concern over the environmental and health impact of unregulated trade in hazardous waste, particularly in developing states. The convention established a framework for regulating the transboundary movement of hazardous wastes and aimed to minimise their generation and disposal (Smith, 2019).

Since the adoption of the 1989 Basel Convention, there has been several amendments and protocols to strengthen its provisions and adapt to new challenges in managing hazardous waste. One notable amendment is the Ban Amendment, adopted in 1995, which prohibits the export of hazardous wastes from developed to developing states for disposal. This amendment was a significant step towards preventing the export of hazardous waste to states with inadequate facilities for their safe disposal (UNEP, 2018).

In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the need to address the root causes of hazardous waste generation and promote more sustainable and environmentally sound hazardous waste management practices on a global scale. The concept of a circular economy, which aims to minimise waste generation and promote the recycling and reuse of material, has gained attraction as a way to reduce hazardous waste trade. International initiatives such as the Strategic Approach to International Chemical Management (SAICM); the 21 October 2001 Waigani Convention, the 1998 Rotterdam Convention, the 1991 Bamako Convention, the 2001 Stockholm Convention, the OECD Council Decision on the Control of Transboundary Movements of Wastes, amongst others, provide legal regimes for the prevention and regulation of transboundary movement of hazardous waste for whatever reasons; essentially to protect human health and the environment (Ansari, et al, 2019; Ogunola, et al, 2020).

These key events, treaties, and regulations have played crucial roles in shaping the landscape of hazardous waste trade by establishing mechanisms for international cooperation, promoting transparency and accountability, and safeguarding human health and the environment. However, challenges remain in ensuring effective implementation and enforcement of these agreements, as well as in addressing emerging issues such as e-waste. The effectiveness of international agreements in regulating hazardous waste trade in African states has been mixed. One of the key limitations is the lack of capacity and resources in many African states to effectively implement and enforce these agreements. This often result in weak regulatory frameworks and inadequate monitoring of hazardous waste shipments, leading to improper disposal and environmental pollution (Mabunda & Edeme, 2017).

Furthermore, the illegal trade in hazardous waste remains a significant challenge, with criminal networks exploiting regulatory loopholes and weak enforcement mechanisms. This illicit trade not only poses risks to human health and the environment but also undermines the efforts of legitimate authorities to regulate hazardous waste trade.

b. Understanding the International Politics of Trade in Hazardous Waste

Understanding the international politics of trade in hazardous waste is significant due to its implications for environmental sustainability, economic development, and social justice. The intricate dynamics of hazardous waste trade intersect various disciplines and require a nuanced understanding of global governance, environmental regulations, and sustainable practices as demonstrated hereunder:

First, is the need for environmental sustainability; especially that trade in hazardous waste has direct consequences on the environment, including pollution, soil contamination, and health hazards to local communities (Bürgin & Schemel, 2017). Second reason dwells on the need for economic development in that proper management of hazardous waste has enormous impact on economic development among African states, particularly, in influencing investment decisions, trade relations, and industrial practices. It is also crucial for policymakers and stakeholders to navigate the balance between economic growth and environmental protection, fostering sustainable development practices in the way (O'Connor, 2015); and,

Third, is on social justice because it borders on the premise that hazardous waste trade often raises concerns over environmental justice, as communities disproportionately affected by pollution and waste disposal may face social inequalities and health risks. Examining the international politics of hazardous waste trade in African states shed light on issues of environmental equity, community empowerment, and the need for transparency in decision-making processes (Zhang, 2018).

c. Stakeholder Perspectives on Trade in Hazardous Waste

Stakeholder perspectives and interests in hazardous waste trade vary significantly by their diverse roles and motivations. Government regulators are key stakeholders with a mandate to enforce regulations and ensure compliance with environmental and health standards (UNEP, 2021). On the other hand, industries that generate hazardous waste may have conflicting interests. Some industries may view hazardous waste trade as a cost-effective solution to disposal and compliance challenges. However, concerns have been raised over the potential for companies to use trade as a means to evade stricter regulations in their home states, leading to environmental degradation in receiving nations (UNEP, 2021).

Environmental groups, on their part, often oppose hazardous waste trade due to the inherent risks it poses to ecosystems and human health. They advocate for stricter regulations and a shift towards sustainable waste management practices. Furthermore, pro-environmental groups also advocate for the cooperation of local communities situated near hazardous waste facilities or transport routes that are directly impacted by these activities (Ogunola, et al. 2016).

Like pro-environmental groups, non-governmental organisations (NGOs) also play crucial roles in advocating for the interests of affected communities and pushing for stronger regulations and engaging in oversight functions in attempt to curtail hazardous waste trade. NGOs often collaborate with local communities to raise awareness, monitor trade activities, and hold stakeholders accountable for their actions (UNEP, 2021). International organisations such as the United Nations Environment Programme work towards establishing global frameworks to govern hazardous waste management practices (UNEP, 2021).

In contrast, some private interests including recycling companies partake in hazardous waste trade as an opportunity for obtaining raw materials for recycling processes. By participating in hazardous waste trade activities, these companies insist they contribute to reducing the environmental burden of waste disposal. However, the challenges lie in ensuring that the recycling processes are conducted responsibly and do not lead to further environmental harm in the recipient states (Ogunola, et al, 2016).

The International Politics of Trade in Hazardous Waste in Africa

An ensuing power dynamics and diplomatic relations play significant roles in shaping the international politics of trade in hazardous waste in Africa. Amongst others, historical legacies, economic interests, regulatory frameworks and geopolitical considerations influence the power dynamics in hazardous waste trade (Wynne, 1989). Essentially, the importance of power differentials in shaping environmental governance is emphasised as more dominant and powerful

states and other actors often exert influence over regulatory processes and decision-making. This power dynamics impacts how regulations are formulated and implemented; which benefits the interests of the more powerful actors involved in hazardous waste trade (Dryzek & Schlosberg, 2017). This manifests in unequal bargaining power between African states and wealthier states of the global North and their transnational corporations (TNCs).

Diplomatic relations between African states and global actors also impact on the regulation and management of hazardous waste trade. Obviously, policy differentials in environmental regulations promote trade in hazardous waste (Kellenberg, 2012). In this context, African states often grapple with conflicting pressures from different stakeholders, including other states, and non-state actors like TNCs and international organisations in the face of diverse international environmental treaties and agreements that shape this ever-unfolding diplomatic interactions (Moss, 2018). Apparently, these diplomatic negotiations influence the ratification and enforcement of international conventions or environmental agreements such as the Basel Convention on the Control of Trans-boundary Movements of Hazardous Waste and Their Disposal.

Moreso, economic interests and incentives also play significant roles in shaping the power dynamics in hazardous waste trade. It is obvious that economic incentives do influence decision-making and thus shape diplomatic relations with global actors involved in hazardous waste trade. Hence some African states derive economic gains from importing hazardous waste for recycling or disposal, despite the associated environmental and health risks (Sarr & Baram, 2017). The pursuit of economic gains obviously outweighs environmental concerns; and which of course explains the complex interplay of factors that shapes the politics of trade in hazardous waste.

At the risk of repetition, power dynamics and diplomatic relations among African states and global actors are pivotal in shaping the international politics of trade in hazardous waste in Africa. However, what considerations or explanations are identified and responsible for explaining how global factors influence decision-making and governance in the management of hazardous trade in waste products. The underlisted explanations are being identified as being culpable in explaining how external actors influence decision-making and governance among African states over trade in hazardous waste:

a. Historical context

Historical context of power dynamics and diplomatic relations among African states and global actors in shaping the international politics of trade in hazardous waste is crucial in understanding the complexities and challenges faced by African states in managing trade in hazardous waste. Colonial legacies and ties have continued to influence relations between African states and global actors shaping trade in hazardous waste. No doubt, colonialism has had a profound impact on the power dynamics of hazardous waste trade in Africa through the exploitation of natural resources, coupled with the imposition of unequal trade relations by colonial powers that has left a lasting legacy of economic dependency and imbalanced power relations between African states and their former colonial masters (Akere, 2019).

Furthermore, a legacy of historical exploitation of African resources has also influenced diplomatic relations with global actors involved in hazardous waste trade. The legacy of economic disparities and the perception of Africa as a dumping ground for hazardous waste has shaped how African states negotiate with foreign states, their governments and TNCs in regulating the transboundary movement of hazardous waste (Agyei-Mensah, 2016). In this whole gamut of unequal trade relations, the historical context of environmental injustice and the ensuing social inequalities in hazardous waste trade cannot be overlooked. The disproportionate burden of environmental degradation and health risks borne by toxic impacted communities in Africa reflects power differentials and diplomatic interests over social and environmental considerations (Narteh, 2018). Indeed, an understanding of this skewed historical context is essential for policymakers, researchers, and environmental activists seeking to address the challenges of hazardous waste management and promoting environmental sustainability in Africa.

b. Regulatory frameworks

Effective regulatory frameworks, both at national and international levels, play critical roles in shaping power dynamics and diplomatic relations among African states and global actors in the international politics of trade in hazardous waste on the African continent. The need to explore the significance of regulatory mechanisms in influencing decision-making processes, fostering cooperation, and addressing power differentials in hazardous waste management cannot be overemphasised (Kellenberg, 2012).

Nationally, robust regulatory frameworks are essential for establishing standards, guidelines, and enforcing mechanisms to govern the import, export, and disposal of hazardous waste within the borders of a state. This is because strong national regulations provide a foundation for ensuring environmental protection, public health, and social responsibility in hazardous waste trade practices (EPA, 2019). The effectiveness of national regulations is known to influence the power dynamics between governments, industries, and community stakeholders, in shaping how hazardous waste is managed and controlled within the jurisdiction of a state.

Additionally, the harmonisation of national regulatory frameworks with international agreements and conventions is crucial for promoting transparency, accountability, and cooperation in hazardous waste management. International treaties such as the 1989 Basel Convention provides a framework for regulating transboundary movements of hazardous waste and which ensures that exporting and importing states adhere to common standards (Basel Convention, 1989). By synchronising, harmonising and aligning national regulations with international norms, African states can mitigate power differentials, enhance diplomatic relations, and foster mutual trust with global actors in hazardous waste trade.

The efficacy of regulatory frameworks in shaping power dynamics and diplomatic relations are underscored by their role in promoting dialogue, negotiation, and collaboration among stakeholders involved in hazardous waste management. Clear and enforceable regulations create a level playing field for all parties; especially in enabling African states to engage in meaningful discussions with global actors on hazardous waste trade practices, and sustainable environmental responsibilities (UNEP, 2020). Additionally, regulatory coherence and compliance contribute to

building trust and credibility among states into trade in hazardous waste, which fosters stronger diplomatic ties and cooperative partnerships in addressing shared environmental challenges.

In essence, the effectiveness of regulatory frameworks at national and international levels, is instrumental in shaping the power dynamics and diplomatic relations among African states vis-à-vis global actors into trade in hazardous waste. Chiefly, prioritising regulatory alignment, enforcement, and collaboration, African states should be empowered to navigate the complexities of hazardous waste management, promote environmental sustainability, and uphold their interests in a globalised waste trade landscape.

c. Environmental justice

Trade in hazardous waste presents a complex and challenging issue of environmental justice (EJ) for African states, as they navigate the dynamics of power and diplomacy with global actors. Environmental justice is crucial in that it emphasises equitable distribution of environmental benefits and burdens, as well as fair treatment in environmental decisions-making processes. In the context of trade in hazardous waste, EJ plays the role of determining how the impacts of trade in hazardous waste are distributed among different communities, particularly within African states (Kazakeviciute & Juodkaite, 2019).

African states, like many other developing states, often become destinations for hazardous waste due to lax regulations and lower costs of disposal (Kellenberg, 2012). This creates a situation where toxic impacted communities, often the most vulnerable and least equipped to deal with the negative environmental and health impacts, bear the brunt of these activities. Principles of EJ insist on a reevaluation of these power imbalances and advocate for the inclusion of the voices of marginalised communities in decision-making processes related to hazardous waste trade (Pellow & Brulle, 2005).

The salience in environmental justice is that it underscores a deeper understanding of the complexities and challenges faced by African states in managing and regulating trade in hazardous waste; which often do open up potential avenues for promoting more equitable and sustainable practices in the handling of hazardous waste with profound implications for policy-making and international cooperation.

d. Geographical considerations

The location of African states; especially, their proximity to major global markets, and the presence of natural resources all impact the dynamics of hazardous waste trade on the continent. The geographical location of the African continent in relation to other continents influences the involvement of global actors in hazardous waste trade; especially that powerful states and their TNCs usually exploit or capitalise on geographical factors to gain control over waste disposal sites or to export waste to regions with less regulatory oversight (Kellenberg, 2012). These actions often perpetuate a cycle of environmental injustice, environmental unsustainability, public health, adverse economic development and place a disproportionate burden on African states that lack the resources and institutional capacity to effectively regulate trade in hazardous waste (Watts, 2012; Adam, 2018).

Be that as it may, the uneven distribution of hazardous waste facilities and disposal sites within Africa often lead to disparities in environmental burdens and risks among different regions and states. This uneven distribution also give rise to tensions and conflicts over the disposal of waste, as states may seek to offload their waste onto neighbouring states with lax regulations (Batur, 2019). A deeper understanding the interconnectedness of geography, power, and diplomacy in the context of hazardous waste trade in Africa, there is need to develop more informed policies and strategies to promote sustainable development and environmental justice in Africa.

e. Transparency and accountability

The primacy of transparency and accountability in trade in hazardous waste is not farfetched. For example, transparency in hazardous waste trade, amongst others, (a) it provides access to information, data, and decision-making processes related to waste management practices; (b) it increases the visibility and public awareness of African states on hazardous waste trade activities; (c) it enables stakeholders to hold governments and global actors accountable for their actions; (d) it helps to build trust between governing bodies, industry stakeholders, and local communities; (e) it fosters positive relationship and promoting cooperation in addressing environmental challenges associated with trade in hazardous waste (Gore, 2018).

Accountability is equally important in shaping the power dynamics and diplomatic relations in trade in hazardous waste. Establishing clear lines of responsibility and mechanisms for oversight holds actors involved in waste management accountable for their actions and decisions. When adequate accountability measures are in place, African states can ensure that regulations are enforced, environmental standards are upheld, and the rights of affected communities are enforced (Jones & Smith, 2019). Accountability fosters a culture of responsibility and ethical conduct, which can influence diplomatic relations with global actors who prioritise environmental stewardship and adherence to international norms.

Conclusion

This paper examines the intricate dynamics and ramifications of the trade in hazardous waste. It also explores the diverse roles played by state parties and private entities, including transnational corporations (TNCs) in the hazardous waste trade. It reveals power imbalances in the trade in hazardous waste between exporting and importing states, illegal dumping occurs frequently, and that African states have difficulty enforcing environmental laws and holding transnational corporations into hazardous waste trade culpable for their deeds.

It further highlights the critical needs for improved stakeholder cooperation, more openness, and stronger regulatory frameworks in order to reduce the detrimental effects of hazardous waste trading on the environment and impacted communities and advance sustainable development in the continent. Overall, the paper advances scholarly knowledge of the intricate network of environmental, political, and economic variables influencing the global politics of the trade in hazardous waste in Africa.

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